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MINE-EMI

MARITIME INNOVATIVE NETWORK of EDUCATION
for **EMERGING MARITIME ISSUES**
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**INNOVATIVE EDUCATION FOR
EMERGING MARITIME ISSUES**

Varna 2021

**CPMR
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Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions

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The international scientific conference "Innovative education for emerging maritime issues" is conducted on 25.02.2021 in the framework of Multiplier event of the project MINE-EMI (Maritime innovative network of education for emerging maritime issues) hosted by Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy (NVNA), Varna.

The aim of the conference is to outline the emerging maritime issues that the authors have identified and want to include in the developed master's programs in the framework of the MINE-EMI project – Port and ship operations, Integrated maritime policy and Port and maritime logistic.

The presented materials were discussed and advocated by the conference participants from Marine Cluster Bulgaria, Conference of the Peripheral Maritime Regions and Piraeus Municipality. All the presentations are accepted for publishing in the conference proceedings.

The conference proceedings preparation is supervised by assoc. prof. Nedko Dimitrov – NVNA coordinator of the project.

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Application of virtual online techniques in maritime education in a pandemic – new pedagogical environment and issues.

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Abstract At present, most maritime educators in pandemic and anti-epidemic measures have to conduct their classes online or at least those subjects that could be taught remotely. Teaching migrates in videoconferencing, but the modern educator could use virtual reality, which is more fully consistent with the theory of experiential learning. The purpose of the article is to expose some approaches to using virtual reality in favor of the educational process. The author reveals gaps in video conferencing and the pros and cons of VR. In conclusion, proposals are made to study further the potential of virtual reality for the training of marine personnel in distance learning.

Keywords—*Virtual Reality, distance-learning environment, maritime education, VR simulator, skills, pandemic*

INTRODUCTION

We are experiencing a worldwide pandemic situation with many restrictions. Globally, the anti-epidemic measures are for everyone, not regarding each age category's different risk factors[1]. The maritime industry is an essential element of the global socio-economic environment[2]. Due to its specifics, it is defined as a risky industry, which requires every aspect of its operation to be strictly regulated, including qualified personnel training.

Fig. 1. Main goals of the article.

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Traditionally, maritime education is conducted in face-to-face classes. In the conditions of COVID-19, this had to be changed, and at the same time, programs must meet precisely set international requirements. A necessary condition for both face-to-face and online classes' success is the learner's active participation [3].

Especially in a pandemic, maritime education's constant task is to update teaching methods in harmony with digitalization and modern technologies[4]. According to the curriculum, a considerable proportion of the specialized maritime subjects are conducted on simulators, reflecting budget expenditures considerably[5], [6]. However, these simulators and laboratories are usually located inside maritime education institutions' territory.

We live in a world that combines the physical world with the virtual one. Practically every physical object could have its "virtual twin" and humans their "virtual avatars" [7]. Many platforms are used effectively to exchange learning materials and give the trainees instructions [8]. For this article and its main goals, fig. 1, The author focused on the controlling idea that states modern e-learning maritime pedagogical environment could promote skills relevant to maritime industry and society.

CRITICAL SKILLS IN THE MARITIME SECTOR AND VIDEOCONFERENCING TEACHING GAPS

The main document that regulates seafarers' international training and qualification is the STCW Code. At the same time, many maritime educational institutions have the status of higher education institutions and, in addition to professional training, also provide an educational qualification degree - bachelor, master, and even Ph.D. All of that is a basis to enrich and expand maritime personnel training in all areas of knowledge, skills, and attitudes(KSA's) relevant to the maritime profession.

Fig. 2. knowledge, skills, and attitudes(KSA's) relevant to the maritime profession [9].

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The "Body of Knowledge " developed by the International Association of Maritime Universities (IAMU) provides specific identification and classification of the maritime industry's required skills[9]. The book divides them into four main categories visualized in fig. 2.

Seafarers conduct most of the operations in a social context as part of the crew. In the maritime industry, technical skills are used in a social environment, where soft skills are required. According to the statistics, most ship accidents are due to the human element and result from organizational factors, technologies, and work environments[10]. The online training task is to transfer knowledge, understanding, and instructions to the learners and boost their professional-soft skills.

Fig. 3. Videoconference teaching vs. Virtual reality classroom according to "Experiential learning theory" [11][12].

According to the experiential learning theory based on Kurt Lewin, John Dewey, and others, there are four learning modes: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation[13]. These modes create a holistic learning environment where gaining new skills results from the interaction between trainees and the environment. In the case of COVID-19 and social distance, a lot of educational stakeholders(lecturer, learners, and others) shift to the videoconferencing learning environment, which regarding the experiential learning theory, has a gap in the mode "Reflective observation" fig.3[11]. To fill this gap, educators should use another learning-related feature: recording and playback, chat, or virtual hand-raising, with a low level of immersion and delay response[11]. To cope with this gap, pedagogical designed experiences developed in virtual reality learning environments better meet the requirements of experiential learning theory fig.3[12].

VR is a promising modern technology and alternative to videoconferencing, but it is in development and has several disadvantages, which must be considered fig.4 [14]. Often, beginners' experience shows a period of adaptation with the technology and motion sickness initially. As a good advantage, the level of social presence is shown in fig.5 [15], making VR a capable solution in pedagogical learning scenarios to acquire professional-soft skills.

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Fig.4 . Virtual reality (Headset) pros & cons vs. Videoconferencing[14].

Fig. 5. Social Presence Score: Immersive VR(Headset) vs. Non-immersive VR vs. Videoconferencing[15].

EXAMPLES OF VIRTUAL REALITY ENVIRONMENTS AND APPROACHES IN LEARNING

This section will demonstrate some examples of use cases of Virtual reality learning environments. As a basis for the environment, the author uses open-source web-based social platform Mozilla Hubs[16]. Typically, most virtual reality applications are heavy and require a powerful and robust hardware configuration, but this is not the case with Mozilla Hubs. The virtual environment is loaded directly into the browser and can be used on various devices - VR headsets, desktop, or mobile devices. Figures 6 and 7 demonstrate and describe possible uses of the VR platform combined with other software to enrich the pedagogical environment and experience[16][17][18][19]. For this purpose, the author demonstrates the ability to load additional 3D objects. In this case, the imported 3d asset is a monument that the author has generated by photogrammetry based on images taken with an unmanned aerial vehicle(UAV or drone). The educators can use the demonstrated combination of various software in the context of maritime education in the following cases:

- Explaining with improved immersion Port infrastructure
- Ship structure – types of ships and onboard equipment.
- Interaction with the environment

- Flexible creation and importing of virtual(3D) assets
- Virtual Generalization of the lessons to the real world
- Better communication – better social presence of the participants
- Role-playing scenarios – relevant to the maritime context.
- And others

SCREENSHOT from Mozilla Hubs Room
Used scene: Outdoor Meetup – made by Hubs Team
3D asset: 3d model of the monument to the patron of the Bulgarian Naval Academy, Nikola Vaptsarov, Varna - made by photogrammetry of images taken with a drone (unmanned aerial vehicle)
Software for photogrammetry: Open Drone Map – free and open source software, URL: <https://www.opendronemap.org/>
Software for streaming: Open Broadcaster Software (OBS) - a free and open-source cross-platform streaming and recording program

Fig. 6. Example of Social VR platform Mozilla Hubs for remote lecture scenario – 1[16][18][17].

The following fig.7 demonstrates the possibility of applying "virtual reality in virtual reality" by broadcasting the instructor's actions in real-time from another virtual reality application - in this case, the simulator VR Regatta for immersive sailing and handling sailboat or yacht[19].

SCREENSHOT from Mozilla Hubs Room
Used scene: Outdoor Meetup – made by Hubs Team
3D asset: 3d model of the monument to the patron of the Bulgarian Naval Academy, Nikola Vaptsarov, Varna - made by photogrammetry of images taken with a drone (unmanned aerial vehicle)
Software for photogrammetry: Open Drone Map – free and open source software, URL: <https://www.opendronemap.org/>
Software for streaming: Open Broadcaster Software (OBS) - a free and open-source cross-platform streaming and recording program URL: <https://obsproject.com/>
Used simulator: VR Regatta – immersive virtual reality simulator for sailing – URL: <https://marineverse.com/vr-regatta-the-sailing-game>

Fig. 7. Example of Social VR platform Mozilla Hubs and Simulator VR Regatta for "Virtual reality in Virtual reality" scenario – 2[16][18][17][19].

Both examples aim to show the possibilities of technology and direct the modern pedagogue to approaches for more creative and practical application of accessible technologies in online

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learning. Specialized VR applications for distance teaching, workshops, VR seminars, and others are also available on the market. VR technology for the mass consumer is available on the market relatively recently, and new developments are yet to come.

CONCLUSION

The article identifies critical skills for the maritime professional and some opportunities for creating and implementing a virtual learning environment for online teaching. At present, maritime education institutions still seem to be investing heavily in infrastructure and on-site simulation complexes, but in a pandemic, this may not be a sufficient enough move. Virtual reality has its place in the process of maritime skills transfer, but education management processes must be knowledge-based[20]. To increase the readiness of maritime education to meet the challenges of future pandemics more effectively in the conditions of distance/blended learning, the author proposes the following:

- Further study of the potential, advantages, and disadvantages of VR technology in the context of maritime education.
- Further study of marine skills which could be effectively acquired in Virtual Reality Learning Environment.
- Developing framework of Maritime Virtual Reality Learning Environment for distance learning according to relevant knowledge, skills, and attitudes – KSA's.
- Developing relevant VR maritime educational experiences.
- Training teachers to handle VR technology freely and creatively.
- Hiring software developers with experience in virtual reality development or training of marine instructors have such skills.

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